

Some Recent Advances in the Chemistry and Reactions of Humic Substances*

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ORGANIC matter occurs in all terrestrial and aquatic environments on the earth's surface. The importance of soil organic matter C in terms of the C cycle as major source of CO₂ and as C reservoir sensitive to changes in climate and atmospheric CO₂ concentrations has been emphasized by recent estimates of Bohn¹. According to him¹, the mass of soil organic C (30.0×10^{14} kg) more than equals those of other surface C reservoirs combined (20.8×10^{14} kg). The decay of soil organic matter provides the largest CO₂ input into the atmosphere. It is true that deeper C deposits in the form of marine organic detritus, coal and petroleum, deep sea solute C and C in sediments are much larger, but these are physically separated from active interchange with surface C reservoirs¹.

It has been estimated that 70-80% of the organic matter in predominantly inorganic soils consist of humic materials, i.e., humic acid (HA), fulvic acid (FA), and humin. The remainder is referred to as non-humic substance—mainly composed of polysaccharides and protein-like substances. Thus, humic substances are the major components of soil organic matter.

Important characteristics of all humic materials are their ability to form water-soluble complexes with metal ions and hydrous oxides, and to interact with minerals and a wide variety of organic compounds including alkanes, fatty acids, dialkyl phthalates, pesticides, herbicides, proteins, carbohydrates, etc. Of special concern is the formation of water-soluble complexes of FA with toxic metals and organics which can increase the concentrations of these constituents in soil solutions and natural waters to levels that are far in excess of their normal solubilities.

Although the importance of humic substances in both agriculture and environmental sciences is beyond doubt, the main stumbling block in understanding their properties and reactions lies in our inadequate knowledge of the chemical structure of humic substances which makes it difficult to interpret experimental data with confidence.

The methods that are currently in use for the characterization of humic substances can be divided into non-degradative and degradative ones (Table 1).

TABLE 1

Non-degradative methods	Degradative methods
1. Functional group analysis ²⁻⁸	1. Elemental analysis ^{2,17}
2. IR spectroscopy ⁴⁻⁶	2. KMnO ₄ oxidation ^{9,51}
3. Absorption spectroscopy (UV and visible) ^{2,9-11}	3. CuO-NaOH oxidation ^{5,21,53}
4. Fluorescence spectroscopy ¹²⁻¹⁴	4. CuO-NaOH + KMnO ₄ oxidation ⁵³
5. NMR (proton and C ₁₃) ¹⁵⁻¹⁷	5. CuO-NaOH + KMnO ₄ + H ₂ O ₂ oxidation ^{53,54}
6. ESR ¹⁸⁻²⁰	6. Peracetic acid oxidation ^{55,56}
7. Electron microscopy (transmission and scanning) ²¹⁻²⁴	7. HNO ₃ oxidation ⁵⁷
8. X-ray analysis ^{9,25}	8. Alkaline nitrobenzene oxidation ⁵⁸
9. Radiochemical methods ²⁷	9. Na-amalgam reduction ^{59,60}
10. Electrometric titrations ²⁷⁻³¹	10. Zn-dust distillation ^{61,62}
11. Viscosity measurements ³²⁻³⁸	11. Hydrolysis with 2 N NaOH ⁶³
12. Osmometric measurements ^{39,40}	12. Hydrolysis with 6 N HCl ^{61,64}
13. Surface tension and surface pressure measurements ⁴⁰⁻⁴³	13. Hydrolysis with H ₂ O ^{63,64}
14. Ultracentrifugation and diffusion measurements ⁴⁴⁻⁴⁷	14. Pyrolysis-gas chromatography ⁶⁵
15. Gel filtration methods ⁴⁷	15. Thermal analysis : DTG and DTA ⁶⁶
16. Light scattering measurements ⁴⁸	16. Radiochemical degradation ⁶⁷
17. X-ray scattering measurements ⁴⁹	17. Biological degradation ⁶⁸
	18. UV, electron, and γ -irradiation ^{69,70}

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Analytical characteristics of humic substances :

On the basis of numerous analyses done on HA's and FA's extracted from soils formed under widely differing geographic and pedological conditions, it is possible to compute⁷¹ the elemental and functional group composition of a 'model' HA and FA (Table 2). The main differences between the two

TABLE—2

ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS		
%	HA	FA
C	56.2	45.7
H	4.7	5.4
N	3.2	2.1
S	0.8	1.9
O	35.5	44.8
Total	100.4	99.7

FUNCTIONAL GROUP ANALYSIS		
meq/g	HA	FA
Total acidity	6.7	10.3
COOH	3.6	8.2
Phenolic OH	3.9	3.0
Alcoholic OH	2.6	6.1
Quinonoid C=O } Ketonic C=O }	2.9	2.7
OCH ₃	0.6	0.8

OPTICAL PROPERTIES		
E ₄ /E ₆	HA	FA
	4.8	9.6

are that: (a) the 'model' HA contains approximately 10% more C but 10% less O than does the 'model' FA; (b) there is little difference between the two materials in H, N and S contents; (c) the total acidity and COOH content of the FA are appreciably higher than those of HA; (d) both materials per unit weight contain approximately the same number of phenolic OH, total C=O and OCH₃ groups, but FA is richer in alcoholic OH groups than HA; (e) the higher E₄/E₆ ratio of FA than that of HA is indicative of lower particle size of the former.

HA and FA degradation products :

In general, oxidative degradation has been found to be most productive in shedding light on the main structural components that make up humic materials. Recent advances in the development of efficient gas chromatographic-mass spectrometric-computer systems, which make possible the separation as well as the qualitative and quantitative identification of micro amounts of organic compounds in complex mixtures, have greatly helped in these respects.

The oxidative degradation of HA's, FA's and humins, from widely differing environments, produces mostly aliphatic, phenolic and benzenecarboxylic acids. In addition smaller amounts of

n-alkanes, substituted furans and dialkyl phthalates can also be identified. The most abundant aliphatic degradation products are n-fatty acids (especially the n-C 16 and n-C 18 acids) and di- and tricarboxylic acids. Major phenolic acids produced include those with between 1 and 3 OH groups and between 1 and 5 COOH groups per aromatic ring. Prominent benzenecarboxylic acids are the tri-, tetra-, penta-, and hexa-forms. These structures constitute the major 'building blocks' of HA's and humins.

The major types of chemical structures⁷¹ that make up the 'model' HA and FA are shown in Table 3. The model 'HA' contains approximately

TABLE—3

MAJOR CHEMICAL STRUCTURES IN 'MODEL' HA AND FA		
Major Products	HA (%)	FA (%)
Aliphatic	24.0	22.2
Phenolic	20.3	30.2
Benzenecarboxylic	32.0	23.0
Total	76.3	75.4
Ratio phenolic	1.6	0.8
Aromaticity	6.9	7.1

equal proportions of aliphatic and phenolic structures, but a greater percentage of benzenecarboxylic structures or structures producing benzenecarboxylic acids on oxidation. By contrast, the 'model' FA contains more phenolic than aliphatic and benzenecarboxylic structures. Both the 'model' HA and FA contain approximately equal proportions of aliphatic structures; both of them are of similar aromaticities.

Thus the 'model' HA and FA have similar chemical structures, except that the FA is richer in phenolic but poorer in benzenecarboxylic acids than the HA.

The chemical structure of humic substances :

From the available experimental data¹⁷, it appears that up to 50% of the aliphatic structures in HA's and FA's consist of n-fatty acids esterified to phenolic OH groups. The remaining aliphatics are made up of more 'loosely' held fatty acids and alkanes that seem to be physically adsorbed on the humic materials, and which are not structural humic components, and possibly of aliphatic chains joining aromatic rings. As shown by a wide variety of chemical degradation experiments, the major HA and FA degradation products are phenolic and benzenecarboxylic acids. These could have originated from more complex aromatic structures or could have occurred in the initial humic materials in essentially the same forms in which they were isolated, but held together by relatively weak bonding. If the latter hypothesis is correct, then the

phenolic and benzenecarboxylic acids would be the 'building blocks' of humic materials and future research should be directed toward finding out how the 'building blocks' fit together and what type of structural arrangement is produced. If, on the other hand, the degradation products originate from more complex chemical structures, further research should be concerned with developing milder degradation methods that would permit the isolation and identification of larger fragments of the total structure.

Structural information from physicochemical methods :

Physicochemical methods provide clues as to what structural arrangement is the most probable one. Scanning electron microscopy²⁴ and viscometry^{25,26} show that both the shape and size of HA and FA particles are strongly affected not only by $pH^{24,25}$ but also by neutral salt concentrations²⁶. At low pH , HA and FA molecules tend to aggregate^{17,21} forming elongated fibres and bundles of fibres. Mostly intermolecular hydrogen bonding appears to be responsible for such aggregation; however, van der Waals forces and interactions between π -electrons of adjacent aromatic rings also play some role. As the pH increases, these forces become weaker. Increasing ionization of COOH and phenolic OH groups induces the particles to separate and repel each other electrostatically so that the molecular arrangements become smaller and smaller but better oriented. Thus there is aggregation at low pH and dispersion at high pH^{22} . However, at pH higher than neutrality, there is some association¹¹ via homolytic bonding due to an increase in free radical content with increasing pH^{20} . On the other hand, with an increase in the ionic strength of the medium, the FA or HA molecules become coiled and their particle sizes are markedly reduced²⁶. At pH levels and neutral salt concentrations prevailing in agricultural soils, HA's and FA's behave like flexible linear macromolecules, so that we are dealing here not with chemical structures largely or exclusively composed of condensed rings, but with numerous linkages about which relatively free rotation can occur.

It becomes thus more apparent that humic substances are not macromolecules or polymers built up of identical monomeric units or structural units but rather combinations, associations or aggregates of different structural units of microbiological, polyphenolic, lignin and condensed lignin origins. These are the benzenecarboxylic and phenolic acids referred to earlier as 'building blocks'. In HA's and humins the 'building blocks' appear to be more complex and stable than in FA's²¹. But in all cases the forces holding the 'building blocks' together are similar, consisting mainly of low-energy bonds. The importance of intra- and intermolecular hydrogen bonds in holding together constituent molecules within a 'so-called' aggregate, and linking 'so-called' aggregates with each other, has recently been highlighted^{7,8}.

X-ray analysis²⁷, viscometry^{7,8}, and electron microscopy (both transmission²⁸ and scanning²⁴) all point to a relatively 'open', flexible structure perforated by voids of varying dimensions that can trap or fix organic and inorganic substances that fit into the voids, provided that the charges are complementary, and that can also interact with these substances on its surface.

Partial chemical structure of FA : A proposal :

In harmony with many of the requirements described before, a partial chemical structure of FA is proposed. This is shown in the figure. This molecular arrangement may account for a significant portion of the FA structure. Although van der Waals interactions and π - π bondings are also likely to be present, bonding between the 'building blocks' is mainly through hydrogen bonds—which makes the structure flexible, permits the 'building blocks' to aggregate and disperse reversibly, depending on the environment, viz. pH , ionic strength, presence of metal ions, etc.; moreover, this structure permits the humic substances to interact with inorganic and organic soil constituents either via oxygen-containing functional groups on the large external and internal surfaces, or by trapping them in internal voids which appear to be less hydrophilic than the external surfaces.

Partial chemical structure of FA.

The chemical structure and reactions of humic substances have been the subject of researches for nearly two centuries, yet much remains to be learned about these materials. While the recent availability of advanced and sophisticated instruments has assisted in generating important information on the 'building blocks' that make up humic substances, more needs to be known on how the 'building blocks' align and what structural arrangement they produce. The main task that confronts researchers in this field at the present time is to develop a valid concept of the chemical structure of humic substances. Once this has been achieved, it will be possible to understand the behavior of these materials in soils and waters, and one will be able to predict how humic substances will affect major chemical and biochemical reactions that occur in these systems. This will obviously benefit soil science, practical agriculture and the environmental sciences.

SCHNITZER & GHOSH : SOME RECENT ADVANCES IN THE CHEMISTRY AND REACTIONS ETC.

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